

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B434
 Date: 3 Mar 2009
 Take Off: 17:03:00
 Landing: 21:06:36
 Flight Time: 4h 03m 36s

Campaign: APPRAISE

Operating Area:

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	Manchester University	
5	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
6	Core Chem	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics 1	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
8	Wet Nephelometer / PSAP	Simon Osbourne	FAAM	
9	AMS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	
10	Manchester Cloud	James Dorsey	Manchester University	
11				
12				
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				

The following log sheets are not available for this flight :

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Xchat	No log available
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	No In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump / filter info included on Flight Summary page
Filters	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
Wet Neph	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	30 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

no data on BADC 30 Dec 2009

B434 17:17:05-21:11:14

GLon_PARA0611, GLat_PARA0610

Sortie Brief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies

Date: 03 Feb 2009

B433 (double flight): t/o (Cranfield) 11:00z, land (Exeter) 15:15z

B434: t/o (Exeter) 16:45z, land (Exeter) 20:45z

M.Sci: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in frontal clouds in association with the Chilbolton radar facility.

Sortie Location: Over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. Area Alpha.

Sortie Summary: Perform a series of runs at a series of altitudes below cloud base (if possible), within and above the cloud, along the azimuth that is being scanned by the radar. Information on the run orientation and altitude to be flown will be provided by scientists at Chilbolton using VHF radio (call-sign "Radsearch"). Where the radar identifies a small-scale feature of interest, the aircraft may abort a long leg in order to turn to re-penetrate it. Where either the aircraft or radar identifies a particular horizontal layer of interest, the aircraft may fly a sawtooth pattern so as to provide a sequence of profiles through it. It is desired that the aircraft flight legs start/finish in the Chilbolton overhead. This benefits the validation of vertically-pointing radar/lidar retrievals of supercooled cloud layers. This requires turns to be done within controlled airspace and so may limit the number of occasions that this is possible.

Sortie Detail B433:

- a) Take off & climb to FL100 to transit to operating area at Chilbolton.
- b) When at suitable location descend from transit altitude to 1000ft agl, or to lowest altitude allowed by operating restrictions. Fly 10min **clear air** leg in vicinity of Chilbolton.
- c) Perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/min along the azimuth and through the cloud system up to FL330 or to above cloud top, whichever is lower.
- d) Fly a series of 40-60km level flight legs along the azimuth scanned by the radar at altitudes defined by the radar or as determined from previous profile. Ideally, just above cloud base, throughout the cloud, just below and just above cloud top. Duration of each leg ~10 minutes. Legs should extend over Chilbolton. During incloud legs AMS should sample off CVI inlet unless tip iced up (but sample off Rosemount inlet out of cloud). Filters to be exposed on out of cloud legs only.
- e) Where the radar identifies a feature of interest or one that is penetrated by the aircraft along any leg, the leg may be interrupted to fly one or more butterfly patterns. Each butterfly consists of a minimum of two minutes straight/level that includes penetration of the feature followed by turns that allow re-penetration of the feature during the reciprocal part of the pattern.
- f) Where a defined layer of interest (such as a shallow layer of supercooled liquid water) is identified by the aircraft or radar, the long leg may be flown as a sawtooth leg with ascents/descents at 1000ft/min, extending 1000ft above and below the layer level (M.Sci may request level segments of 1 minute).
- g) Repeat items d) to e) as long as flight endurance or cloud conditions permit.
- h) End with below-cloud clear air aerosol leg (10 min) if possible, before recovering to destination airfield.

Sortie Detail B434:

As above except for takeoff and transit from Exeter airfield onto Chilbolton Radial to begin science, landing back at Exeter.

PROJECT BRIEF: APPRAISE-Clouds – mixed-phase cloud studies

Scientific Aims: The purpose of this project is to obtain detailed microphysical measurements in stratiform cloud systems, altocumulus clouds, wave clouds and cumulus clouds within the temperature regime in which ice particles will likely co-exist with liquid (typically 0 to -30C).

The flight plans are designed to characterise the aerosol above and below the cloud and infer aerosol fluxes into the cloud layer by combination with the vertical wind measurements and the microphysical characteristics within the cloud layer.

Constant altitude flight legs of approximately 50 km (10 minutes flying) will be made:

- In the boundary layer to measure the aerosol size distributions (from 10 nm to 100 um), CCN, aerosol composition from 30 nm to 1 um using the ToF AMS; larger particles and non-volatile material such as refractory material will be measured using EDAX analysis of filter samples.
- Near cloud base within cloud to measure the cloud droplets that have been activated from CCN, interstitial particles and larger particles that have fallen from cloud top. In addition the onset of ice will be observed using the CPI, CAPS and 2-D probes in cloud.
- Middle of the cloud passes will be made at temperatures where key processes will be expected to be initiated (-6C to -9C) for the Hallett-Mossop process or around -15C where fragmentation of dendritic crystals may be important.
- Near cloud top and within the cloud to measure entrainment and aerosols within entrained eddies and ice particles within the cloud; in colder clouds ice initiation will occur in this region.
- Above the cloud to measure the properties of aerosol particles that can potentially be entrained into the clouds.

In-situ measurements from the aircraft are performed in close coordination with the CAMRa radar and lidar facilities at Chilbolton, Hants.

Weather conditions: Stratiform, or altocumulus clouds lying over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. This may or may not be generating precipitation at the surface. It is particularly desirable if the mean wind direction lies between about 220 and 280 degrees. This allows the aircraft to fly legs along the radar beam whilst staying closely parallel to the mean wind direction.

Key instruments and their operation.

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer, CR2
- GPS, GIN, turbulence probe – When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud/Aerosol Physics/Chemistry

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops (>100micron) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- 2DS, CAPS and FSSP – as above
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where a run is only partially in cloud and is starting in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Manager's log.
- TWC. If possible, a profile in clear air is desirable for calibration purposes.
- AMS, SMPS/WCPC (- to sample off Rosemount inlet)
- Filters

Mission Scientist Debrief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies:
Flight Number: B434, 3rd March 2009 (Take-off 17:02z, landing 21:06z at Exeter)
Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims & operating area: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in frontal clouds in association with the Chilbolton radar facility.

Weather conditions: The conditions leading up to take-off for the second flight B434 on March 3rd are described in the flight B433 debrief. The wave that developed on the cold front out to the SW earlier in the day generated a warm front which by 18:00z had moved across Wales and SW England and was now lying approximately over the top of Chilbolton at this time. The low which had formed at the apex of the wave was now over north Wales (Anglesey), and the trailing cold front lay across the west coast of Wales and over the tip of Cornwall (Fig 1). At take-off the operational area (Exeter-Chilbolton) lay within the main band of precipitation associated with the system (Fig 3). Take-off, 17:02z occurred as soon as possible after refuelling at Exeter (following B433). The duration was limited by the remaining available flight crew hours which required a landing to occur by ~20:45-21:00z. The whole of this flight therefore took place during the maximum extent/depth of cloud cover, which precluded any below cloud/clear air legs.

Figs 3 and 4 (left to right) showing rainfall over the UK observed at 17:45z and 21:00z respectively

Fig 5 : IR satellite picture 18:00z 030309

Fig 6 : IR satellite picture 21:00z 030309

Summary of the flight: Prior to and following take-off (as on flight B433) there were problems with the Horace logging system which persisted for the first 12 minutes or so of the flight (halfway into R1) and which resurfaced at times during the flight (eg ~17:40-17:43z). In order to maximise the coverage of the full depth of the cloud, within a limited amount of time, a slightly different flight strategy was followed on this flight. On inbound legs to Chilbolton (CH) (where ATC required us to approach controlled air-space beyond (east of) Chilbolton at a fixed altitude declared many minutes ahead of time ie during the inbound leg) constant altitude legs would be flown. However, on outbound legs towards the SW (on the 255° radial from Chilbolton) a sawtooth profile would be carried out between 2000ft below and 2000ft above the mean altitude of the leg. It was envisaged, that this would give maximum coverage of the variability in cloud microphysics with altitude, while still providing statistically significant data. The sawtooth (including an initial climb up to the bottom level of the sawtooth) was started soon after passing overhead CH on the outbound radial. At a profiling rate of 1000ft/minute, this enabled around 1.5 sawtooths per outbound leg, ending up at the upper sawtooth level at the SW end of the leg. The last climb was generally continued into the turn to arrive at the altitude of the next inbound SLR run, generally 1000ft above the top altitude of the outbound sawtooth leg. The initial run, inbound to CH, was carried out at 3500ft. Prior to starting R1, heavy (solid) precipitation (ppt) was encountered. At times R1 was near to cloud base (CB). It was also noted that there was a temperature (T) gradient from E to W, with T decreasing by about 0.8°C from the start to end of R1. Details of the subsequent inbound SLR legs and outbound sawtooth profiles are summarised in the following tables.

After R1 (3500ft) the first set of sawtooth profiles was set P1.x (outbound) initially between 3500ft up to FL80, down to FL40, up to FL80 and back down to FL60 at the end of the outbound leg (profiles P1.1, P1.2, P1.3 and P1.4 respectively). This gave measurements in the temperature range 0.7 to -7.0°C. During the turn at the SW end of

the track, a profile climb P2 (from FL60) up to FL90 was carried out to run back inbound to CH at FL90 (725mb, -7.3°C). After passing CH outbound a second set of sawtooth profiles (P3.x) was undertaken, initially from FL90 up to FL140, down to FL100 (giving measurements over the temperature range -6.6 to -15.5°C) and finally up to FL150 (P3.1, P3.2, P3.3 respectively). R3 was then started in the SW turn to run back inbound to CH at FL150 (572mbar, -17.8°C). (N.B. see the Mission Scientist flight log and screen dump file for more details).

Essentially, unlike flight B433 in which the approaching warm front cloud was mostly totally glaciated down to the freezing level (possibly due to seeding crystals dropping in from higher cirrus above), in this flight the aircraft passed through regions containing significant amounts of supercooled liquid water in pockets alongside ice in the form of columns and large crystals (aggregates and snowflakes), along with some dendrites and possibly fragmented crystals (due to shattering on probes?). Higher up (FL150, ~ -18°C) the probes saw some plates and possibly bullet rosettes. During this sequence the radar at Chilbolton reported seeing regions of high dbz at 20-40km range and around 3.0-3.5km (11.5kft) possibly indicating a supercooled water layer (probably as a result of embedded convection), so it was decided to investigate this feature next. After passing CH outbound a profile descent (P4) to FL115 was undertaken and SLR R4 commenced (655mbar, -10.8°C). The reciprocal inbound leg (R5) was carried out at FL110 (667mbar, -10.4°C). Similar regions of supercooled water mixed in with a whole spectrum of ice crystals were observed, however at one point (18:50z) cloud particle concentrations suffered a dramatic increase. There were also places which were quite bumpy (turbulent) but this did not necessarily tie in with observations of supercooled liquid water each time. Table 1 summarises this first sequence of profiles and runs, which was completed by the P6.x sawtooth profile series between FL90 and FL130 to fully examine the feature observed by the Chilbolton radar (in case the chosen altitudes for R4 and R5 missed the region of interest).

Table 1 – Sequence 1 of SLR and Sawtooth legs during B434

P # Run #	u/d in/out bound (I/O)	Flight level	Initial Pressure (mbar)	T(°C) start/end for SLR	Comments/observations
R1	I	3.5kft	889	+2.3 s +1.5 e	(on QNH 994) near cloud base (CB) over-head Chilbolton (CH)
P1.1 u	O	3.5kft FL40 FL60	890 874 810	+1.5 +0.72 -2.16	
P1.2 d	O	FL80 FL60	754 810	-7.0 -4.8	Chilbolton reports CT 6500m (21.3kft) Melting layer at 1km (3.3kft) and windshear at 3.8km (12.5kft) CoreCloud (CC) saw columns 17:24z
P1.3 u	O	FL40 FL60	872 811	-0.69 -19.7	FL40 Highest cones ice so far 250-300 litre ⁻¹ (previously ~100 litre ⁻¹)
P1.4 d	O	FL78	756	N/A	Horace problems (no T/Td or ff/dd)

		FL60	811	-6.4	
P2	O/turn	FL60 FL90	811 725	-6.4 s -7.3 e	
R2	I	FL90	725	-7.3 s -6.6 e	Captain 226°/65kts (turb 223°/46m/s) CPI lots large lumps of ice, PIP 3mm snow + CPI sees supercooled water (also 2DC) CH high reflectivity 15dbz at 3.5km (11.5kft) poss liquid water Turb probe iced up 17:56z *** CC/CPI conclude in/out water regions - R2
P3.1 u	O	FL90 FL120	724 643	-6.6 -11.7	Aircraft anti-icing – ice detection too
P3.2 d	O	FL140 FL119	596 644	-15.5 -12.0	Captain 230°/58kts (turb * 258°/38m/s) CC large chunks ice, CPI huge fragments + dendrites
P3.3 u	O	FL101 FL120	693 643	-8.5 -11.7	CPI conc 5cm ⁻³ (CPC 60cm ⁻³)
R3	I	FL150	572	-17.8 s -17.9 e	Chilbolton – lumps high dbz 3.0-3.5km (10-11.5kft) 20-40km range, high melting layer at 2.5km (8.2kft) ?? CT 7.5km (24.5kft) feature at 3.5km (11.5kft) [so will examine feature next]# CC sees plates + chunks >900µm CPI- too large to see + small (200µm) ice then CPI sees columns/rosettes
P4 d	O	FL150 FL130	571 617	-17.9 -13.8	Very low QNH so FL will be higher than normal altitude (FL115=10.75kft) CC poss liquid at FL120 (655mb, -12°C)
R4 #	O	FL115	655	-10.8 s -11.2 e	CC see snowflakes at start R4 then CC/CPI see spell of liquid water Chilbolton Ci up to 8km (26.3kft) with fall streaks to 3.5km (11.5kft) 2DC jump from 50-60 L ⁻¹ to 300 L ⁻¹ CAS went through roof too CIP/CAS concs 0.5/45 cm ⁻³ FSSP 25-30cm ⁻³ Feature ? Bumpy – but no water same time
P5 d R5	I	FL110	667	-10.4 s -9.8 e	CAPS LWC 0.1-0.2 g m ⁻³ CPI seeing plates + small lumps (shattered fragments?) PIP aggregates 2mm across 2DC 1800 L ⁻¹ snowflakes/columns CAPS 15µm & 200µm modes OH CH spell liquid water both CC/CPI Then CPI sees water + hex plates
P6.1 d	O	FL110	669	-9.8	
P6.2 u	O	FL90 FL110	721 669	-6.6 -9.5	
P6.3 d	O	FL130 FL100	622 694	-13.5 -9.1	Massive increase particle concs – mostly ice ~120 cm ⁻³ mostly columns
P6.4 u	O	FL90 FL110 FL130	722 669 618	-6.8 -10.1 -14.0	Chilbolton RHI – convective feature moving towards CH range 60km

After completing the first sequence of SLRs and sawtooth legs, a profile ascent (P7) up to FL200 (465mbar, -30.0°C) was undertaken (starting in the turn at the SW end of the radial) to begin investigation of the upper levels of the cloud system. At FL141 the CPI saw hexagonal plates and hailstones that appeared to have been rimed. At FL180 the CPI saw small aggregates, hex plates, the occasional needle and some very large “stuff”. Core cloud confirmed aggregates of 800µm or so. Upon reaching FL200 a brief descent (P8) to FL180 was carried out, and the inbound leg completed as SLR R6 (504mbar, -25.1°C). Near the CH end of R6 bullet rosettes were observed, over the region that the radar was observing the convective “feature” in.

Table 2 – sequence 2 of SLR and Sawtooth legs during B434

P # u/d Run #	in/out bound (I/O)	Flight level	Initial Pressure (mbar)	T(°C) start/end for SLR	Comments/observations
P7 u	SWturn	FL130	618	-14.0	FL141 CPI Hex plates + rimed hailstones FL180 CPI small aggs of Hex plates + occ needle + some very large stuff CC aggregates ~800µm
		FL150	570	-18.3	
	I	FL170	525	-22.9	
	I	FL192	480	-28.1	
P8 d	I	FL200	465	-30.0	
R6	I	FL180	504	-25.1 s	Bullet rosettes – above feature?
P9	O wide turn	FL180	505	-25.2	CH feature 35km W CTs 2.5km(8.2kft) - CPI pristine B.Rosettes; PIP ice 0.2-1mm - Can see stars at FL250 – CPI Pristine tiny bullet rosettes + faceted spheres
		FL217	432	-34.4	
		FL252	372	-42.0	
		FL280	329	-49.7	
R7	I - wide	FL300	300	-55.0 s -55.4 e	Flight Man called LW probes on way up 2DS briefly stopped – cold Rapid descent to next level
R8	I	FL250	373	-41.8 s -41.3 e	CH reports nothing above 4km ?? Shear at 5.5km (18kft) 50-100km west. Rapid descent to next level
P10.1 d	O	FL200	462	-30.5	
P10.2 u	O	FL160	547	-20.7	
P10.3 d	O	FL200	465	-30.0	Ch report feature CT 2km(6.5kft)
P11 d	SWturn	FL160	Missed	Missed	Continuation of P10.3 CH convective feature 5-8km west CH
R9	I	FL90	723	-7.3 s -7.9 e	CC – low concs water drops CPI sees drops + aggs (inc dendrites) a/c anti-icing ice detection, 2DC – columns Very bumpy near CH, PIP large number particles +Columns + agg + pockets water CDP sees water, 2DS agrees
P12.1	O	FL90	722	-7.9	v. bumpy at start P12.1 – sees CPI lots of columns + water; CC agrees
		FL60	809	-3.8	
P12.2	O	FL40	871	0.1	At CB here CPI/AMS saw lot liquid
		FL60	811	-3.4	
P12.3	O	FL80	754	-6.5	Breaking clouds at FL68 -end of science RTB
		FL61	807	-3.7	

Following the turn at CH a profile ascent (P9) was initiated after passing CH outbound in an attempt to get to above CT and to investigate the origin of particles potentially seeding lower levels. CPI again observed pristine bullet rosettes at about 35km out from CH (at FL217, 432mbar, -34.4°C) while PIP saw large particles over the size range 200µm to 1mm. This was directly above the feature observed at lower levels by the radar. At FL252 (372mbar, 41.9°C) the cloud was very thin and stars could be seen above. CPI saw pristine tiny bullet rosettes and faceted spheres. Shortly afterwards, Flight manager found a clear air slot to zero the condensed water probes in, but in general there was still thin cloud around so the profile was continued up to FL300 (turning at the SW end of the run at FL288) which seemed to be just through CT. At this level a short inbound SLR R7 was started (300mbar, -54.9°C) and 2DS returned to working order after being briefly affected by the cold temperatures. To maximize the time left on task a rapid descent to FL250 was instigated, and the inbound leg completed as R8 at FL250 (373mbar, -41.8°C) to further characterize the high level cold cloud sections.

The radar reported they could see little of interest above 4km (13.1kft), but at 50-100km range saw a shear layer at 5.5km (18kft). In view of this, on the outbound leg, a rapid descent to FL200 was undertaken, and a sawtooth series P10.x between FL200 and FL160 carried out to investigate the feature observed by the radar. P10.1, P10.2 and P10.3 down from FL200 (462mbar, -30.5°C) to FL160 (547mbar, -21.0°C), back up to FL200 and back down to FL160 respectively, were fitted in before the SW turn. During the turn P10.3 was continued as P11 down to FL90 (723mbar, -7.3°C), and the inbound leg carried out as R9 at FL90 to overhead CH. During P11 (at the SW end of the inbound leg - at the end of the turn) there was a period of turbulence between FL120 and FL110. During the early part of R9, CC reported low levels of liquid water, and CPI saw aggregate crystals, including dendrites. Later, however, CDP saw water drops as did 2DC and the aircraft anti-icing system detected water too. Earlier on, CH had reported embedded convection at 8-10km range from CH. In this region during R9, 2DC reported columns at the same time as the a/c anti-icing detecting water. In the turn northeast of CH it was quite bumpy. PIP saw large numbers of precipitation (3mm) sized particles, and these were mixed in with columns, aggregates and pockets of liquid water. CDP saw more water and 2DS agreed with this observation.

Finally, an investigation of the lower cloud regions was undertaken by carrying out a final sawtooth profile series P12.x initially from FL90 down to FL40 (P12.1), then back up to FL80 (P12.2) and finally back down to FL60. At the start of P12.1 it was very bumpy, CPI saw lots of columns and supercooled water. CC concurred. At FL40 (871mbar, 0.1°C), the aircraft was coming out of CB and there was a great deal of liquid water present here at this zero degree level. At the end of P12.3 (FL61/807mb, -3.7°C) the aircraft began its approach to Exeter airport, landing at 21:06z. On this occasion the weather at Exeter was considerably better (than for the landing on B433) with little crosswind to affect the landing. Figures 7 and 8 below indicate the regions of enhanced condensed water and the aircraft altitude as a function of time respectively for most of this flight.

Figs 7 and 8 (left to right) showing condensed water loadings and aircraft altitude respectively for B434

Notes on instrumentation:

As for flight B433, significant problems were encountered at the start of the flight because the Core Data logging system, Horace, suffered a number of dropouts. Reliable data recording was established towards the end of R1. Because of the amount of supercooled water present throughout this flight, the turbulence probe partly iced up by the end of R2 (~17:56z) and remained so for most of the flight. 2DS became affected by the cold for a few minutes towards the end of profile P9 until the end of R7 (at FL300), but recovered during the rapid descent to FL250.

Mission Scientist's Log [APPRAISE-CLOUDS]

Flight No B...434 Date ...2/23/09... Name K.N. BOWER Page ...1 of ...10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
16:54.57	(KNS)	- XX:XX-XX			Engine Start 4-1
16:57.16	"				Power change over
16:58.43	"				Taxi (QNH 994)
17:03.12	"				Rolling
17:03.44	"	2780'			T/O pouring rain.
					CB
				***	Horace has problems again ***
17:07.40	≡	17:08:32 KNS		(+52 sec)	Time Check
					Solid ppt
17:10.27	R1	3.5kt	262	50°42'/3°24'	889mb 2.29°/3.94° (117°/259°) **
17:15.29	R1	3.5kt	262	50°42'/3°24'	890mb 2.35°/3.35° (115 mls/260°) **
17:20.41	R1	3.5kt	82	51°0'/1°42'	890mb 1.79°/3.55° 21mls/216°
17:23.11	R1	3.5kt	84	51°6'/1°24'	(OH OH) 890mb, 1.47°/3.26° 31mls/206°
					Near CB. (NS T gradient W→E)
17:27.00	R1	3.5kt	205	51°6'/1°18'	890mb 1.53°/3.52° 28mls/200°
17:28.00	R1	3.5kt	225	51°6'/1°18'	891mb 1.50°/3.55° 26mls/199°
17:30.16	R1E/PI	3.5kt	240	51°6'/1°30'	Core E-Solid (approx 4000ft)
					CPI-.....
					Will start back
17:30.49	PI.1	FL 40	241	51°6'/1°36'	874mb 0.72°/2.47°C 30mls/197°
17:31.43	PI.1	FL 50	244	51°0'/1°36'	842mb -0.54°/0.66°C 30mls/209°
17:32.47	PI.1	FL 60	246	51°0'/1°42'	810mb -2.16°/-1.36°C 28mls/212°
17:33.46	PI.1	FL 70	245	51°0'/1°48'	780mb -4.94°/-3.27°C 27mls/213°
17:34.44	PI.1/PI.2	FL 80	245	51°0'/1°54'	754mb -7.0°/-5.03°C 26mls/209°
17:35.46	PI.2	FL 70	247	51°0'/2°0'	783mb -6.79°/-3.53°C 29mls/211°

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Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 434 Date 03/03/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 2 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Chitkuten: 6500 ft
					(3.3kt) ← 1000 m Melting layer
					Wind shear at 3800 m (12.5kt)
✓ 17.36.41	P1.2	FL 60	243	51°0'/2°0'	810mb -4.82°/-1.63° 30m/s/213°
✓ 17.37.41	P1.2	FL 50	244	51°0'/2°6'	840mb -3.51°/+0.18° 32m/s/208
✓ 17.38.15	P1.2	FL 44	244	51°0'/2°6'	860mb -2.28°/1.35°C 32m/s/208
✓ 17.38.38	P1.2E/ P1.3	FL 40	243	50°54'/2°12'	872mb -0.69°/2.17°C 31m/s/209
					for higher ones of ice solar.
					250-300 L ⁻¹ - (below 100 L ⁻¹)
100% ✓ 17.40.52	P1.3	FL 60	242	50°54'/2°18'	811mb. (207.92°/70.93°) (1218m/s/268) * * *
100% ✓ 17.42.06	P1.3	FL 72	243	50°24'/2°21'	Columns - 775h (208°/70.93°) (1154m/s/253) * * *
100% ✓ 17.42.49	P1.3E/ P1.4	FL 78	244	50°54'/2°30'	756mb (208°/70.93°) (1136m/s/243)!! * * *
✓ 17.45.00	P1.4E/ P2	FL 60	244	50°54'/2°42'	811mb, -6.4°/-1.35°C 30m/s/233
[SW] ✓ 17.46.00	P2	FL 68	246	50°48'/2°42'	turning 785mb -6.61°/-2.9°C 28m/s/214
✓ 17.46.14	P2 only/ R2	FL 90	132	50°54'/2°42'	725mb, -7.31°/-6.47° 46m/s/223°
					226°/65kts Ceptans (Wind speed/dur) ↑ not too bad.
					CPT - lots really large lumps of ice here
					C.Chut: P1P 3mm - snow flakes.
					super-cooled water - CPT
					ce - 2DC seeing water too.
→ 17.51.16	R2	FL 90			723mb -7.4°/-5.95°C (63m/s) -182° ??
					Radsearch -
					Rad Reflcts 3500nm 15 dbz (11.5kt)
					poss supercooled water.
→ 17.56.08	R2				Turbulence probe read up. again

(216/55kts - Wind speed)

for hydr u

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...434 Date 03/03/09 Name K.N. Bower Page 3 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
[CH] 17.57.43	KNB	FL 90			OH OH unband.
[CH] 18.04.00	KNB	FL 90	246	51°6'/1°24'	OH OH 723mb -6.65°/-6.4° (25/241)
					CPI - after brief consultation - Core Clear - in / out / in water regions.
18.05.23	R2E/P3.1	FL 90	246	51°6'/1°30'	724mb -6.61°/-6.4°C (26m/s/239)
	P3.1	FL			A/C range detected icing too.
18.06.23	P3.1	FL 100	247	51°6'/1°36'	696mb -8.44°/-8.02 (30m/s/256)
18.07.26	P3.1	FL 110	246	51°0'/1°42'	666mb -10.13°/-9.84° (53m/s/285)
18.08.20	P3.1	FL 120	247	51°0'/1°48'	643mb -11.74°/-11.67 (73m/s/294)
18.09.19	P3.1	FL 130	248	51°0'/1°48'	618mb -13.56°/-13.39 (108m/s/302)
18.07.49	P3.1	FL 115	247	51°0'/1°42'	656mb -10.89°/-10.52 (62m/s/291)
18.10.09	P3.1E/P3.2	FL 140	247	51°0'/1°54'	596mb -15.51°/-14.72 (115m/s/302)
18.11.21	P3.2	FL 130	250	51°0'/2°0'	619mb -13.82°/-14.23 (50/281)
					230/38 kts (258/38 - high) Carbin
18.12.28	P3.2	FL 119	248	51°0'/2°6'	644mb -11.95°/-11.28
					large chunks of ice CC here.
					CPI - some dendrites - huge fragments
18.14.13	P3.2E/P3.3	FL 101	247	50°54'/2°15'	693mb -8.45°/-7.77° (40/220)
18.15.27	P3.3	FL 110	248	50°54'/2°24'	669mb, -10.18°/-8.93 (25/252)
18.16.24	P3.3	FL 120	249	50°54'/2°30'	643mb, -11.73°/-11.49° (32/270)
					CPC 60 cm ⁻³
					CPI 5/cm ⁻³
18.17.28	P3.3	FL 130	248	50°54'/2°30'	618mb -13.59°/-13.64 (48/291)
18.18.25	P3.3	FL 140	249	50°54'/2°36'	574mb -15.74°/-16.04 (57/293)
[SW] 18.19.22	P3.3E/P3.3	FL 150	248	50°48'/2°42'	572mb -17.71°/-17.19 (57/294)

↑
(Exciter 998 GHz)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...434 Date 03/03/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 4 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
				Chitbolton.	reports → 3000-3500m 20-40km range. seem to be N's High dbz → lumps of high dbz
					[226/57 kts] Captains report wind speed/direction (27m/s)
			→	Change to Feet - Omaha (10,000 - 11,500 ft)	high melting 2500 m (8.2 kft) might be cirrus
					<u>Radsar</u> - CT's ~ 7500m (24.5 kft) feature 3500m (11.5 kft)
					(^a will return W at 11.5 kft and E at 11.0 kft)
18.31.48	R3	FL150	80°	51°6'/1°24'	(ON CH) 572mb -17.78°/-17.19 — cloud - seem plates now. + chunks - large than 800m-900 CFI - too large for CIP to see + small ice 200µm
18.36.43	R3	FL150	241°	51°6'/1°24'	(ON CH) 571mb, -18.07 / -17.5 (Smts/95) CFI column/wiselt
18.38.09	R3E/P4	FL150	251	51°6'/1°30'	571 mb, -17.9 / -17.42°C
18.39.08	P4	FL140	247	51°6'/1°36'	592 mb, -15.95 / -16.12°C
18.40.11	P4	FL130	247	51°0'/1°42'	617 mb -13.83 / -13.64°C
					v low ANM ° FL - detects high altitude *
18.41.10	P4	FL120	249	51°0'/1°48'	poss Liquid Core Cloud -11.97°/-11.83° p = 655mb

[→ odds east-bound
← evens west-bound]

* FL - flight levels will be higher altitude than normal

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....⁴³⁴ Date ...03/03/09... Name K.N. BOWER Page 5 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
16.41.42	R4E/R4	FL115	247	51°0'/1°48'	655 mb, -10.78°/-10.53°C Core Cloud - pretty smallish now.
16.45.30	R4	FL115	248	50°54'/2°12'	altitude is 10750 ft (750ft lower than FL)
16.47.	R4	FL115.			2hrs left [Spell of liquid water CC & CP?] Chubbathin - Ci up to 8km. (26.3kft) fall streaks 3500m (11.5kft) reflections - goes to 1200m Core Cloud, 2DC - 50-60 → 300 μm^{-1}
16.50.16	R4	FL115	250	50°54'/2°36'	CAS - went through roof!! [-11.45°/-10.32°C CAP 0.5 cm^{-3} (656mb CAS 45 cm^{-3} 40s ags CAP - occasional proper spectrum LW or FSSD ~ 25-30 cm^{-3} Ice???
16.51.14	R4				Burning - no water through (CC or CP)
17.52.13	R4E/PS	FL115	249	50°48'/2°42'	656mb - 11.19°/-10.48°C (50/83°)
18.52.41	PS/RS	FL110	278	50°48'/2°48'	667mb - 10.35°/-9.99°C (58/115) LWE 0.1-0.2 g/m^3 CAPS hot wire CPI - seeing plate like things on CPI - rest is very small lumps - shattered fragments? Cloud - aggs 2mm across concs ~ 1400 μm^{-1} 2DC habits - Snowflakes, Columns. CAPS - 15 μm 200 μm 2 modes. 2: ~1000 μm

#

[SN]
C

3 cycles left after this one. ⇒ 6 levels/legs.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 434 Date 03/03/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 6 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					AMS-
[CN] 19.03.25	RS	FL110	80	51°6'/1°24'	(ON CN), 669mb -9.95°/-9.41°C
19.06.50	RS	FL110	73	51°6'/1°12'	turning, 669mb -10.32/-6.65°C
					Another spell liquid H ₂ O - 15s (Cloud)
					OPI-
[CN] 19.10.47	RS	FL110	240	51°6'/1°24'	(ON CN) -9.7°C/-9.66°C (8m/s/163°)
					OPI - better supercooled H ₂ O + Hex p/bts
✓ 19.11.55	RSE/P6.1	FL110	252	51°6'/1°30'	669mb -9.8°C/-9.52°C (21m/s/214°)
✓ 19.12.58	P6.1	FL100	250	51°6'/1°36'	696mb -7.91°C/-7.92°C (30m/s/210°)
✓ 19.13.54	P6.1E/P6.2	FL90	247	51°0'/1°36'	721mb -6.0°C/-5.72°C —
					Mission 2 -
✓ 19.15.17	P6.2	FL100	247	51°0'/1°42'	693mb -8.07°/-7.73°C —
					at end of this Westward leg 3 cycles left
					left
✓ 19.16.16	P6.2	FL110	250	51°0'/1°46'	669mb -9.59/-9.72°C
✓ 19.17.27	P6.2	FL121	249	51°0'/1°54'	639mb -11.92/-12.2°C
✓ 19.18.06	P6.2E/P6.3	FL130	247	51°0'/2°0'	622mb -13.52/-13.12°C
✓ 19.19.22	P6.3	FL120	249	51°0'/2°6'	642mb -12.15/-11.96°C
✓ 19.21.35	P6.3	FL110	247	50°54'/2°18'	696mb -9.14/-8.1°C
					massive increase - particle concentrations
					mostly ice
✓ 19.22.54	P6.3E/P6.4	FL90	247	50°54'/2°24'	722mb -6.83/-6.63 mostly
					peaks 120 cm ⁻³ mostly column
		FL110			vol conc 0.3 g/m ³
✓ 19.24.52	P6.4	FL110	247	50°54'/2°30'	669mb -10.15/-9.45°C (13m/s/222°)

(g)/m³
|
20 cm⁻³
|

Mission Scientist's LogFlight No B. 424Date 03/03/09Name K.N. BowerPage 7 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					PHI - convective feature moving to CH
					- mella layer - 2500m.
					range 60km - on 255°
19.26.56	P6.9E/P7	FL130	248	50°48'/2°42'	618 mb -13.95/-13.35°C
		FL141		(CPI)	Hex plates + hail stones that have been rimed
19.28.55	P7	FL150	109	50°54'/2°42'	570 mb -16.29/-17.30°
19.29.50	P7	FL160	120	50°54'/2°36'	547 mb -20.86/-19.76
19.30.45	P7	FL170	92	50°54'/2°30'	525 mb -22.91/-18.71°
19.31.39	P7	FL180	75	50°54'/2°24'	508 mb -25.12/-23.61°
					OP2 small eggs Hex plates + occ needles + some very large stuff.
					Core Clouds - Aggs - 800µm or so.
19.32.59	P7	FL192	80	50°54'/2°12'	480 mb -28.17°C/-26.32°C
19.33.42	P7end/P8	FL200	79	51°0'/2°6'	465 mb -29.97°C/-25.98°C
					8000 - 3500 (26.2NH - 11.5NH)
19.35.48	P8/R6	FL180	79	51°0'/1°48'	262 . 504mb, -25.09/-26.29°C
19.37.13	R6	FL180	79	51°6'/1°36'	Bullet Rosettes 505 mb, -25.1°/-24.8°
19.38.79	R6.	FL180			(OH CH)
19.40.31	R6	FL180	115	51°6'/1°12'	Penitum 505mb -25.01/-24.9°C
19.43.40	R6/P9	FL180	296	51°6'/1°24'	505mb (OH CH) 505mb -25.21/-24.84°C
19.47.21	P9	FL217	250	51°0'/1°42'	OP7 protine B Rosettes 432mb -34.36/-33.68°C
					PIP :- 1mm → 200µm range.
19.51.12	P9	FL252	297	51°0'/2°6'	372mb -41.92°C/-38.15°C

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 434 Date 03/03/09 Name K.N. BOWLER Page 8 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					35km - range - West Chilbolton
					Tops 2500 m (8.2kft).
					Can see stars /
					depad on!
					Top of cumvortex feature.
					cumms-stepped on !!! phew.
					Flight Manager - cal-ed LW probes - brief clear
					- Probes - long bullet rosettes here <u>air slot</u>
					+ faceted spheres
19.55.26	R4	FL280	246	50°54'/2°30'	329mb -49.71°C/-49.24° -
19.56.50	R4	FL288	251	50°46'/2°42'	turning SW and 317mb -51.83°C/-46.61°C
19.59.06	R4 and R7	FL300	100	51°0'/2°42'	300mb -54.93°/-49.12°C
20.02.00	R7 End	FL300	96	50°54'/2°18'	descent (rapidly) to FL250, -55.39°/-52.77°C, 300mb
					EDS. back now after being too cold. For a while
20.09.15	descent R8 st	FL251	76	51°0'/1°54'	373mb, -41.83/-43.07°C
				[Restart]	Chilbolton - rolling above 4km
					West 80-100 km - shear 5500m
					TWC. - landing? (18kft)
20.07.25	R8	FL250	81	51°6'/1°24'	(ON, ON) 375mb -41.31/-44.27°C
					TWC - back edge aligned with....
20.12.40	R8	FL250	240	51°6'/1°24'	(ON ON) 375mb, -41.22°/-43.71°C
20.13.20	R8 end	FL250	246	51°6'/1°24'	Rapid descent... 375mb, -41.3/-41.85°C

↑
[SW]
C

↑
[ON]
↑
[ON]

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...634 Date 03/03/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 9 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
✓ 20.14.58	P10.1	FL200	252	51°0'/1°36'	462mb (end of rapid descent) -30.47°/30.52°
↑ 20.16.47	P10.1E / P10.2	FL160	246	51°0'/2°0'	547mb, -20.69°/-21.05°C
✓ 20.22.47	P10.2 / P10.3	FL200	245	50°54'/2°24'	465mb -30.03°/-28.59°C
[SW] 20.26.21	P10.3	FL163	274	50°48'/2°42'	541mb -22.14°/-20.42°C (24mb/223°)
↻					CM - feature - tops 2km
					after arrival leg drop down to investigate....
↘ 20.26.49	P10.3 / P11	FL160			missed screen temp data - continued profile as P11
↘ 20.28.22	P11	FL140	120	50°54'/2°42'	593mb, -17.02°/-17.1°C (27mb/212°)
↘ 20.30.24	P11	FL119	91	50°54'/2°24'	646mb, -12.67°/-13.09°C (21mb/245°)
					-bumpy here and following leg....
↘ 20.32.15	P11	FL99	76	50°54'/2°12'	699mb, -8.88°/-9.44°C (37mb/254°)
					Chubbelt; Convective... S-8km West of CM
↑ 20.33.03	P11E/R9	FL90	79	51°0'/2°6'	723mb -7.34°/-7.22°C (23mb/248°)
					CC - low conc Supercooled H ₂ O
					CP1 - eggs (inc dendrites)
					CD1 - sees water drops -20X sees
					all anti icing
↑ 20.37.40	R9	FL90	81	51°6'/1°30'	columns (20X) 723mb, -7.47°/-6.42°C
↑ 20.38.33	R9	FL90	82	51°6'/1°24'	etc anti icing on. 723mb, -7.41°/-7.01°C
[CB] 20.38.55	R9	FL90	79	51°6'/1°24'	(On eh) 723mb, -6.73°/-6.91°C
20.39.49	R9	FL90	345	51°6'/1°18'	Very bumpy 723mb, -7.14°/-6.48°C
					large N ₂ s particles (3mm) on RFP.
					+ columns + eggs
					+ pockets H ₂ O (liq)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 434 Date 03/03/09 Name K.N. BOWEN Page 10 of 10

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
20.42.21	RA	FL 90	200	51°6'/1°12'	CIDP sees more water 723mb, -7.6°/-6.48°C ZDS agrees with CIDP
20.43.30	RA	FL 90	252	51°6'/1°18'	723mb -7.7°C/-6.93°C (New rec'd at 20.00 ???)
(CN) 20.44.10	RA	FL 90	254	51°6'/1°24'	(04 0M) 723mb, -7.39°/-7.06° (Wind bud)
✓ 20.44.41	RAE/PR1	FL 90	248	51°6'/1°24'	722mb, -7.92°/-6.31°C saw both down. At start of descent - V Dumps & CPI lots volume + SC water * Core cloud agrees.
✓ 20.47.05	PR2.1	FL 69	251	51°0'/1°42'	784mb, -3.83°/-3.27°C —
✓ 20.47.55	PR2.1	FL 60	255	51°0'/1°42'	809mb, -3.76°/-3.3°C —
✓ 20.49.10	PR1	FL 48	253	51°0'/1°48'	847mb, -1.21°/-0.97°C —
✓ 20.49.59	PR1E/PR2.2	FL 40	253	51°0'/1°54'	871mb, 0.09°/0.21°C (20mb/232) Coming out of CB here CPI - AMS - saw lot liquid H ₂ O at bottom
✓ 20.51.57	PR2.2	FL 60	253	51°0'/2°6'	811mb, -3.41°/-3.96°C (Turb probe still not OK)
✓ 20.53.14	PR2.2	FL 7.1	252	50°54'/2°12'	776mb, -5.27°/-5.5°C
✓ 20.54.06	PR2E/PR2.3	FL 80	252	50°54'/2°18'	754mb, -6.52°/-6.78°C (11/313) 250/34kts. Captain H/dd
✓ 20.55.29	123	FL 6.8	253	50°54'/2°30'	786mb, -4.98°/-4.27°C - breaking clouds
20.56.17	PR2.3E	FL 60	253	50°54'/2°36'	807mb -3.71°/-3.83°C RTB (QIN n now 956) (Wind 210/08kts)
21.07.27	KNB				landed.
21.13.44	KNB				power change over

Cloud Physics Flight Log B433

Date: 03/03/09	Operator:KFT	DRS Time:16:42	DAU1 Time: Set	DAU2 Time: Set	DAU3 Time: N/A	AUX1 Time: Set	Aux2 Time: Set
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	PCASP		2DC		2DP		CDP		FFSSP		UMan FSSP		PIP	
Operated?	Y		Y		N		Y		Y		Y		Y	
Pre-flight checks	Vref (>7):	4.0	EI#1 V (>1):	-2.0	EI#1V:		Laser V(~3):	4.0	Ref V (~3):	3.7	Laser V (~9):	9.4	EI#1 V:	1.8
	Flow (~1):	0.81	EI#32 V (>1):	-1.7									EI #1V:	3.6
	Pressure:	986											EI#64 V:	2.6
	Temp (NDIT)	9.3												

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			Blocks Tx	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	
17:03																	2dc, CDP, PIP windows wet before take-off HEATERS ON
17:07:01		9	013.	5	700			1	77	140	15	35	20	0.002	900		
17:10:29	3000FT	21	0.11	13	800			1	250	10	40	5	15	0.002	1000		RUN 1
17:13:17	3000FT	50	0.19	8	800			1	328	25	20	10	20	0.001	1000		
17:16:49	3000FT	33	0.19	14	800			1	414	180	18	50	20	0.002	1500		
17:22:00	3000FT	47	0.20	8	600			1	748	280	16	180	18	0.002	1000		
17:25:02	3000FT	26	0.12	17	625			1	896	180	12	100	12	0.002	1000		
17:28:22	3000FT	210	0.08	11	625			1	1064	165	16	100	18	0.002	1000		
17:30:25	3000FT	123	0.09	19	700			1	1146	75	12	75	18	0.01	2400		ICE FROM FL040
17:31:48	FL050	25	0.25	70	650			1,2,8	1186	45	19	20	28	0.01	2300		SAWTOOTHES
17:32:50	FL060	13	0.33	85	800			5,8,9	1196	NOISE		20	35	0.01	2100		
17:34:01	FL070	12	0.50	108	800			11, 8	1204	NOISE		5	32	0.01	1400		
17:35:55	FL070	10	0.38	170	800			9,8	1215	NOISE		5	34	0.01	2600		
17:36:45	FL060	25	0.29	133	775			9,8,1	1223	5	8	50	28	0.01	2700		
17:38:20	FL045	34	0.23	18	800			1,12	1266	66	19	50	20	0.003	1200		
17:39:57	FL050	15	0.13	125	800			8,9	1322	40	29	40	29	0.01	2400		
17:40:56	FL060	32	0.38	136	800			5,8,9	1348	14	21	15	29	0.01	2200		
17:42:55	FL080	2	0.33	138	775			5,8,9	1368	NOISE		5	35	0.07	2400		
17:45:03	FL060	9	0.16	160	750			5,8,9	1391	NOISE		5	33	0.01	2200		
17:46:20	FL070	102	0.25	450	800			5,8,9	1410	NOISE		10	33	0.02	3600		
17:48:17	FL090	12	0.42	188	800			9,8	1433	NOISE		10	33	0.01	2800		

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP Blocks Tx	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	LWC	
17:50:44	FL090	7	0.33	110	550			12,9,8	1465	6	24	10	33	0.002	2700		SUPERCOOLED H2O
17:53:01	FL090	33	0.30	170	800			9,1	1483	5	18	8	32	0.01	1800		
17:54:58	FL090	28	0.32	180	800			9,8,1	1503	1	9	8	32	0.01	1900		
17:57:03	FL090	70	0.20	72	775			9,8,11	1518	NOISE		5	32	0.01	2500		
17:58:55	FL090	55	0.25	115	800			9,8,11	1527	NOISE		8	33	0.01	2400		CBOLTON
18:02:07	FL090	8	0.44	113	800			9,8	1542	NOISE		7	33	0.01	2700		
18:04:08	FL090	12	0.11	85	800			9,8,5	1555	NOISE		7	33	0.01	2400		
18:05:26	FL090	12	0.40	92	775			9,8,1	1562	NOISE		8	33	0.01	2400		SUPERCOOLED H2O
18:06:26	FL100	14	0.31	162	800			9,8	1570	NOISE		10	32	0.01	1600		
18:08:24	FL120	8	0.48	140	800			9,8	1586	NOISE		10	32	0.01	1300		
18:09:24	FL130	11	0.19	60	800			8,11	1591	NOISE		5	31	0.01	900		
18:10:17	FL140	3	0.89	45	800			8,4,11	1593	NOISE		7	31	0.01	900		
18:11:20	FL130	12	0.36	120	800			8,9,11	1599	NOISE		10	30	0.02	1300		
18:12:29	FL120	21	0.37	95	800			8,9,11	1607	NOISE		10	31	0.01	1700		
18:14:16	FL100	38	0.38	160	800			8,9,11	1621	14	17	20	30	0.01	1500		LIQ H2O 181500-181530
18:16:36	FL120	24	0.36	55	800			8,9,11	1640	NOISE		10	30	0.01	1000		
18:17:34	FL130	2	0.20	50	800			8,9,11	1643	NOISE		10	30	0.01	900		
18:19:24	FL150	4	0.91	85	800			8,9,11	1649	NOISE		10	29	0.01	800		START RUN 3
18:21:12	FL150	11	0.15	76	650			8,11	1657	NOISE		10	30	0.02	500		
18:28:46	FL150	20	0.30	100	800			8,11	1686	NOISE		10	30	0.02	800		
18:31:50	FL150	12	0.46	55	750			8,4	1698	NOISE		10	30	0.01	600		
18:35:09	FL150	12	0.44	60	775			8,7,11	1713	NOISE		10	30	0.01	500		ISOLATED PLATES
18:36:53	FL150	7	0.25	60	550			8,9,11	1715	NOISE		10	30	0.01	550		CBOLTON
18:38:13	FL150	11	0.42	70	625			8,4,11	1719	NOISE		10	30	0.01	500		START PROFILE 4
18:39:11	FL140	18	0.35	98	725			8,4	1723	NOISE		10	29	0.02	1000		
18:40:15	FL130	25	0.34	78	800			8,4	1729	NOISE		10	30	0.01	1500		
18:41:45	FL115	8	0.32	60	800			9,5	1741	NOISE		8	33	0.01	2600		
18:44:04	FL115	20	0.32	62	800			9,8	1760	NOISE		8	32	0.01	3500		
18:46:07	FL115	3	0.33	50	750			8,7,11	1774	NOISE		5	31	0.01	1100		LIQ H2O 184500-184520
18:49:02	FL115	27	0.33	180	800			8,11	1802	1	10	20	35	0.01	2200		LIQ H2O
18:52:46	FL110	40	0.29	140	750			8,11	1850	NOISE		10	32	0.01	1800		
18:55:01	FL110	21	0.33	312	800			8,11	1877	NOISE		15	32	0.11	2200		
18:58:00	FL110	20	0.38	160	800			8,11	1927	NOISE		10	32	0.02	1600		V LARGE CONCS 18:56
18:59:26	FL110	38	0.30	170	800			4,8	1838	4	30	15	32	0.01	2000		
19:02:05	FL110	20	0.21	107	800			4,9,8	1955	3	10	10	25	0.01	4300		PIP BIMODAL
19:05:04	FL110	20	0.32	85	800			9,8,7	1978	NOISE		10	32	0.12	3900		LIQ H2O 190630-190700
19:08:04	FL110	10	0.42	65	750			9,8,11	1997	NOISE		10	32	0.01	1200		

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			Blocks Tx	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	
19:09:25	FL110	7	0.35	32	750			1,9,8	2007	18	22	5	32	0.01	2500		LIQ H2O 190830-190930
19:11:03	FL110	10	0.37	100	800			8,11	2014	NOISE		8	32	0.01	1800		
19:11:54	FL110	23	0.46	100	800			8,7,11	2019	NOISE		8	32	0.01	3000		PIP BIMODAL
19:12:59	FL100	40	0.32	136	800			8,9,7,11	2030	0.6	12	10	32	0.01	2600		PIP BIMODAL
19:13:58	FL090	80	0.37	150	800			8,7,11	2041	NOISE		5	32	0.01	2000		LIQ H2O 191400
19:15:20	FL100	5	0.34	50	700			8,7,11	2047	NOISE		5	32	0.01	2500		
19:16:19	FL110	9	0.48	92	800			9,11	2055	1	12	10	33	0.02	1900		
19:17:29	FL120	9	0.61	95	725			9,11	2063	NOISE		10	32	0.01	1500		
19:18:20	FL130	50	0.42	130	800			8,4,9	2067	NOISE		10	32	0.01	1300		
19:19:24	FL120	14	0.39	140	800			9,11,1	2077	1	8	10	32	0.01	1800		
19:20:36	FL110	130	0.27	400	800			9,4,7	2101	NOISE		50	32	0.57	2000		
19:22:42	FL090	60	0.39	240	800			9,4,1	2145	NOISE		10	32	0.04	2300		LIQ H2O 192100
19:24:03	FL100	13	0.38	85	775			9,8,11	2159	NOISE		10	32	0.02	1500		
19:30:48	FL170	2	0.50	50	625			9,8,11	2213	NOISE		10	29	0.02	800		
19:31:42	FL180	2	0.43	73	800			8,11	2218	NOISE		10	28	0.01	500		
19:32:59	FL190	2	0.77	30	885			8,11	2222	NOISE		2	28	0.01	400		
19:33:43	FL200	8	0.07	34	525			8,11	2224	NOISE		4	28	0.01	550		
19:34:46	FL190	3	0.30	80	700			8,4,11	2227	NOISE		5	29	0.01	550		
19:35:49	FL180	11	0.59	70	675			8,4,11	2231	NOISE		5	30	0.01	500		END P8 START R6
19:38:01	FL180	8	0.29	80	675			8,4,11	2237	NOISE		5	30	0.01	420		
19:40:12	FL180	8	0.74	85	750			8,11	2242	NOISE		5	28	0.01	320		
19:43:01	FL180	2	0.64	31	775			8,4,11	2247	NOISE		5	28	0.01	410		
19:44:52	FL190	2	0.32	51	475			8,4,11	2252	NOISE		2	30	0.01	470		PROFILE 9
19:45:44	FL200	5	0.38	77	600			8,4,11	2254	NOISE		4	28	0.01	220		
19:46:37	FL210	2	0.10	43	450			8,4	2255	NOISE		2	26	0.01	300		
19:47:51	FL220	4	0.28	83	450			8,4	2259	NOISE		2	26	0.03	250		
19:48:51	FL230	17	0.1	25	300			8,11	2260	NOISE		2	26	0.02	200		
19:50:04	FL240	188	0.22	100	425			8,11	2263	NOISE		3	28	0.03	100		
19:51:07	FL250	11	0.20	45	425			11	2264	NOISE		2	28	0.03	150		
19:52:25	FL260	12	0.15	80	300			11	2267	NOISE		2	28	0.02	160		
19:53:50	FL270	5	0.11	250	250			11	2272	NOISE		2	28	0.01	150		
19:55:32	FL280	18	0.21	190	275			11	2276	NOISE		2	28	0.01	100		
19:57:19	FL290	20	0.18	130	150			11	2281	NOISE		2	28	0.01	100		THIN LAYER 19:56
19:59:08	FL300	17	0.08	0					2283	NOISE		2	29	0			END PROFILE 9
20:01:37	FL300	3	0.07	11	175			11	2284	NOISE		0		0			
20:04:18	FL250	55	0.17	70	400			8,11	2292	NOISE		1	28	0.01	440		START RUN 8
20:06:14	FL250	80	0.30	35	525			8,11	2295	NOISE		2	26	0.01	230		

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			Blocks Tx	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	
20:07:29	FL250	20	0.36	80	450			8,11	2297	NOISE		0		0.01	130		
20:10:14	FL250	6	0.10	33	325			8,11	2301	NOISE		0		0.01	100		
20:11:59	FL250	6	0.15	13	300			8,9,11	2303	NOISE		0		0.01	180		
20:12:42	FL250	9	0.25	66	725			8,4,11	2304	NOISE		2	27	0.02	250		CBOLTON
20:15:01	FL200	4	0.71	48	475			8	2310	NOISE		2	30	0.02	480		SAWTOOTHES
20:20:57	FL180	8	0.53	93	800			4,8,11	2343	NOISE		8	30	0.01	530		
20:22:01	FL190	7	0.32	65	725			4,8	2347	NOISE		5	29	0.01	500		
20:22:47	FL200	0		93	750			8,4	2350	NOISE		5	29	0.02	300		
20:23:53	FL190	42	0.19	75	500			8,4	2355	NOISE		5	29	0.02	350		
20:25:02	FL180	20	0.34	50	800			8,7,9	2360	NOISE		5	29	0.01	750		
20:25:49	FL170	15	0.48	53	800			8,4	2364	NOISE		7	30	0.01	2500		END SAWTOOTHES
20:27:31	FL150	35	0.23	99	800			8,11	2376	NOISE		5	30	0.01	3000		
20:28:27	FL140	42	0.35	102	800			8,7,4	2382	NOISE		5	31	0.01	3500		
20:30:22	FL120	28	0.40	160	775			8,7,3	2400	0.7	10	12	32	0.02	3800		
20:32:09	FL100	86	0.22	180	800			8,7,3	2417	0.8	10	12	32	0.02	3400		
20:33:08	FL090	98	0.29	212	725			8,9,7	2434	1	8	12	32	0.02	2400		
20:35:07	FL090	40	0.28	150	800			9,8,12	2463								POCKETS LIQ H2O
20:36:37	FL090	193	0.38	500	800			9,8,12	2477	9	45	30	32	0.02	4000		
20:38:26	FL090	380	0.24	1000	800			4	2531			10	32	0.11	5000		POCKETS LIQ H2O
20:40:02	FL090	900	0.21	780	800			4,8	2601	NOISE		50	32	0.35	4500		
20:43:04	FL090	540	0.23	1012	800			4,8,12	2649	60	40	50	32	0.25	5200		LIQ H2O
20:44:24	FL090	550	0.199	730	800			4,8,12	2696	65	45	45	30	0.23	4600		LIQ H2O
20:45:20	FL080	590	0.20	390	750			4,8,12	2730	44	15	50	32	0.03	5600		LIQ H2O
20:47:09	FL070	141	0.20	200	800			9,8,12	2745	1	10	5	32	0.01	1500		LIQ H2O
20:49:00	FL060	35	0.29	122	800			3,1,4,9	2767	NOISE		5	32	0.005	2200		
20:51:08	FL050	19	0.32	100	750			4,1,3	2787	1	5	5	32	0.01	2300		LIQ H2O
20:52:09	FL060	150	0.31	130	775			4,12,8	2794	NOISE		5	32	0.03	1800		
20:54:15	FL080	10	0.25	70	725			12,8,9	2808	11	20	8	30	0.01	2100		LIQ H2O
20:55:23	FL070	37	0.21	40	550			9,8,3	2817	25	13	25	32	0.01	4500		LIQ H2O
20:56:23	FL060	33	0.26	18	750			3,9	2820	NOISE		0		0.005	1800		
21:04																	HEATERS OFF

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP	Vref:	3.98	NOT MUCH USE IN THESE CONDITIONS BUT SEEMED OK
	Flow:		
2DC	EI#1:	-1.9	GOOD IMAGES
	EI#32:	-1.5	
2DP	EI#1:		NOT FITTED
FFSSP	Ref V:	3.4	OK
CDP	Laser V:	3.96	OK. NOISE IN ICE
UMan FSSP	Laser V:	9.4	OK
PIP	EI#1:	1.7	GOOD IMAGES THROUGHOUT. TAS MANUALLY SET TO 100M/S
	EI#32:	3.2	
	EI#64:	2.3	
Rack Equipment			Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.

Flight:

B434

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B434
Date: 03/03/09

Instruments

1. Horace being a pain, this time insertion of the disk sorted the problem!
2. turbulence probe iced in first <0 profile must have got water in it on profile out of exeter
3. 17:55 Horace drop

Issues

Start R1

OH CH

End R1 start P1.1

P1.1 4000ft

P1.1 5000ft

P1.1 FL60

P1.1 FL70

P1.1 end start P1.2

P1.2 FL70

P1.2 FL60

FL50 P1.2

P1.2 FL44

End P1.2 start P1.3

P1.3 FL60

Core cloud - columns

End P1.3 start P1.4

End P1.4 start P2

SW turn

P2 end R2 start

R2 water +3mm snow

R2 - OH CH

End R2, start R3.1

P3.1 FL100

P3.1 FL111

P3.1 FL115

P3.1 FL120

P3.1 FL130

end P3.1 at FL140 start P3.2

P3.2 FL130

P3.2 FL119

End P3.2 start P3.3

P3.3 FL120

P3.3 FL130

P3.3 FL140

End P3.3 start R3

OH CH

Turning at Pepis

OH CH

End R3 start P4

Flight B434 18:39:08
Heading 247 deg Speed 264 knots Height 14.0kft Press 592mb
Lat 51°5.0'N Long 1°36.0'W Wind 11 ms-1/ 169 deg
Temp -15.95C Dewpoint -16.12C
From 17:10:00 to now

Current values
 GIN LONGITUDE -1.65 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
 GIN LATITUDE 51.1 deg (+ve N)

Flight B434 18:40:11
Heading 247 deg Speed 260 knots Height 13.0kft Press 617mb
Lat 51°0.0'N Long 1°42.0'W Wind 13 ms-1/ 141 deg
Temp -13.83C Dewpoint -13.64C
From 17:10:00 to now

Current values
 GIN LONGITUDE -1.74 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
 GIN LATITUDE 51.08 deg (+ve N)

End P4 start R4 at FL115

Spell of liquid water CC & CPI

End R4 start P5

end P5 start R5

R5 - OH CH inbound

turning

R5 - OH CB outbound

Flight Summary B434

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
T/O	17:17:04	262	3.5kft	50.7N	3.4W						17:03:00
Run 1	17:17:15	073	3.5kft	51.0N	2.1W	17:30:19	240	3.5kft	51.1N	1.6W	17:10:29
note	17:23:50	006	3.5kft	51.2N	1.4W						oh chikl 17:23:13
Profile 1.1	17:30:19	240	3.5kft	51.1N	1.6W	17:34:44	245	7.9kft	51.1N	1.9W	
Profile 1.2	17:34:44	245	7.9kft	51.1N	1.9W	17:38:38	243	4.1kft	51.0N	2.2W	
Profile 1.3	17:38:39	244	4.0kft	51.0N	2.2W	17:42:51	243	8.0kft	50.9N	2.5W	
Profile 1.4	17:42:51	243	8.0kft	50.9N	2.5W	17:45:12	246	6.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	
Profile 2	17:45:12	246	6.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	17:48:16	135	9.0kft	51.0N	2.7W	
Run 2	17:48:16	135	9.0kft	51.0N	2.7W	18:05:25	248	9.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
note	17:58:57	082	9.0kft	51.1N	1.7W						chb
Profile 3.1	18:05:25	248	9.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	18:10:11	247	14.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	
Profile 3.2	18:10:11	247	14.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	18:14:15	247	10.1kft	51.0N	2.3W	
Profile 3.3	18:14:15	247	10.1kft	51.0N	2.3W	18:19:25	248	15.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Run 3	18:19:25	248	15.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	18:38:10	251	15.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
note	18:31:48	080	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chill bolton is under us NOW
Video	18:34:37	258	15.0kft	51.1N	1.2W						off, dark
Profile 4	18:38:10	251	15.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	18:41:44	247	11.6kft	51.1N	1.9W	
Run 4	18:41:45	247	11.6kft	51.1N	1.9W	18:52:15	249	11.5kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 5	18:52:16	249	11.5kft	50.9N	2.8W	18:52:44	284	11.1kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Run 5	18:52:44	284	11.1kft	50.9N	2.8W						

End R5 start P6.1

End P6.1 start P6.2

P6.2 FL110

P6.2 FL121

End P6.2 start P6.3

P6.3 FL120

P6.3 FL100

End P6.3 start P6.4

P6.3 FL120

RT SW end P6.4 start P7

P7 FL150

P7 FL160

P7 FL170

P7 FL180

P7 FL192

End P7 start P8

End P8 start R6

Bullet Rosettes

Pepis turn

End R6 start P9

CPI – pristine bullet rosettes

P9 FL252

P9 FL280 flight man cal'ed Nev etc

Turning SW end in P9

FL300 – end P9 start R7

end R7 – start rapid descent to FL250

Start R8 at FL250

OH CB inbound

OH CB outbound

End R 8 start v. rapid descent

Start of sawtooth P10.1

Flight Summary B434

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
T/O	17:17:04	262	3.5kft	50.7N	3.4W						17:03:00
Run 1	17:17:15	073	3.5kft	51.0N	2.1W	17:30:19	240	3.5kft	51.1N	1.6W	17:10:29
note	17:23:50	006	3.5kft	51.2N	1.4W						oh chikl 17:23:13
Profile 1.1	17:30:19	240	3.5kft	51.1N	1.6W	17:34:44	245	7.9kft	51.1N	1.9W	
Profile 1.2	17:34:44	245	7.9kft	51.1N	1.9W	17:38:38	243	4.1kft	51.0N	2.2W	
Profile 1.3	17:38:39	244	4.0kft	51.0N	2.2W	17:42:51	243	8.0kft	50.9N	2.5W	
Profile 1.4	17:42:51	243	8.0kft	50.9N	2.5W	17:45:12	246	6.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	
Profile 2	17:45:12	246	6.0kft	50.9N	2.7W	17:48:16	135	9.0kft	51.0N	2.7W	
Run 2	17:48:16	135	9.0kft	51.0N	2.7W	18:05:25	248	9.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
note	17:58:57	082	9.0kft	51.1N	1.7W						chb
Profile 3.1	18:05:25	248	9.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	18:10:11	247	14.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	
Profile 3.2	18:10:11	247	14.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	18:14:15	247	10.1kft	51.0N	2.3W	
Profile 3.3	18:14:15	247	10.1kft	51.0N	2.3W	18:19:25	248	15.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Run 3	18:19:25	248	15.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	18:38:10	251	15.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
note	18:31:48	080	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chill bolton is under us NOW
Video	18:34:37	258	15.0kft	51.1N	1.2W						off, dark
Profile 4	18:38:10	251	15.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	18:41:44	247	11.6kft	51.1N	1.9W	
Run 4	18:41:45	247	11.6kft	51.1N	1.9W	18:52:15	249	11.5kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 5	18:52:16	249	11.5kft	50.9N	2.8W	18:52:44	284	11.1kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Run 5	18:52:44	284	11.1kft	50.9N	2.8W	19:11:53	252	11.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	
Profile 6.1	19:11:53	252	11.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	19:13:55	247	9.1kft	51.1N	1.7W	
Profile 6.2	19:13:55	247	9.1kft	51.1N	1.7W	19:18:11	247	12.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	

Run 2	17:48:16	135	9.0kft	51.0N	2.7W	18:05:25	248	9.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
note	17:58:57	082	9.0kft	51.1N	1.7W						chb
Profile 3.1	18:05:25	248	9.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	18:10:11	247	14.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	
Profile 3.2	18:10:11	247	14.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	18:14:15	247	10.1kft	51.0N	2.3W	
Profile 3.3	18:14:15	247	10.1kft	51.0N	2.3W	18:19:25	248	15.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Run 3	18:19:25	248	15.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	18:38:10	251	15.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
note	18:31:48	080	15.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chill bolton is under us NOW
Video	18:34:37	258	15.0kft	51.1N	1.2W						off, dark
Profile 4	18:38:10	251	15.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	18:41:44	247	11.6kft	51.1N	1.9W	
Run 4	18:41:45	247	11.6kft	51.1N	1.9W	18:52:15	249	11.5kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 5	18:52:16	249	11.5kft	50.9N	2.8W	18:52:44	284	11.1kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Run 5	18:52:44	284	11.1kft	50.9N	2.8W	19:11:53	252	11.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	
Profile 6.1	19:11:53	252	11.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	19:13:55	247	9.1kft	51.1N	1.7W	
Profile 6.2	19:13:56	247	9.1kft	51.1N	1.7W	19:18:11	247	13.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	
Profile 6.3	19:18:11	247	13.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	19:22:41	247	9.1kft	51.0N	2.4W	
Profile 6.4	19:22:41	247	9.1kft	51.0N	2.4W	19:27:04	260	13.2kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 7	19:27:04	260	13.2kft	50.9N	2.8W	19:33:43	079	20.0kft	51.0N	2.1W	
Profile 8	19:33:43	079	20.0kft	51.0N	2.1W	19:35:48	079	18.1kft	51.1N	1.8W	
Run 6	19:35:48	079	18.1kft	51.1N	1.8W	19:43:42	245	18.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	
Profile 9	19:43:43	245	18.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	19:59:09	102	30.1kft	51.0N	2.7W	
Run 7	19:59:09	102	30.1kft	51.0N	2.7W	20:02:02	096	30.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	Waters zeroed at 19:58
Run 8	20:04:19	077	25.1kft	51.1N	1.9W	20:13:20	246	25.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	
note	20:07:27	081	25.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilbolton
Profile 10.1	20:15:00	252	20.1kft	51.1N	1.7W						

End P10.1 start P10.2

End P10.2 start P10.3

SW Turn

(missed screen dump)

P10.3 changed to P11 at FL160

P11

Bumpy just after here

P11 end R9

columns

Aircraft anti-icing alert on

OH CH

Very bumpy

CDP – water (2DS agrees)

New plot, same times

Flight B434 20:43:30
Heading 252 deg Speed 262 knots Height 9.0kft Press 723mb
Lat 51°6.0'N Long 1°18.0'W Wind 59 ms-1/88 deg
Temp -7.7C Dewpoint -6.93C
From 17:10:00 to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	74610	secs	<input type="radio"/>	All	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sc
—	JW LIQUID WATER CONTENT	0.12	g m-3	<input type="radio"/>			
—	NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER	0.11	g m-3	<input type="radio"/>			
—	NEVZOROV TOTAL WATER	0.57	g m-3	<input type="radio"/>			

OH CH

End R9 start P12.1

P12.1 down FL69

P12.1 down FL60

P12.1 down FL48

End P12.1 start P12.2

P12.2 up FL60

P12.2 up FL71

End P12.2 start P12.3

Breaking clouds

End P12.3 RTB

Flight B434 20:58:07
 Heading 232 deg Speed 263 knots Height 4.5kft Press 857mb
 Lat 50°48.0'N Long 2°42.0'W Wind 37 ms-1/ 293 deg
 Temp -0.25C Dewpoint -2.58C
 From 17:10:00 to now

Current values
 STATIC PRESSURE 857.63 mb
 DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP -0.26 deg C
 DEW POINT -2.59 deg C

Flight B434 20:58:16
 Heading 232 deg Speed 263 knots Height 4.3kft Press 865mb
 Lat 50°48.0'N Long 2°42.0'W Wind 37 ms-1/ 292 deg
 Temp -0.04C Dewpoint -1.07C
 From 17:10:00 to now

Current values
 GIN LONGITUDE -2.79 deg (+ve E)
 GIN LATITUDE 50.86 deg (+ve N) Draw plane

Flight B434 20:58:29
Heading 225 deg Speed 261 knots Height 3.9kft Press 875mb
Lat 50°48.0'N Long 2°48.0'W Wind 39 ms-1/287 deg
Temp 0.32C Dewpoint -0.66C
From 17:10:00 to now

Current values
GIN LONGITUDE -2.8 deg (+ve E) Draw plane
GIN LATITUDE 50.85 deg (+ve N)

Profile 4	18:38:10	251	15.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	18:41:44	247	11.6kft	51.1N	1.9W	
Run 4	18:41:45	247	11.6kft	51.1N	1.9W	18:52:15	249	11.5kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 5	18:52:16	249	11.5kft	50.9N	2.8W	18:52:44	284	11.1kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Run 5	18:52:44	284	11.1kft	50.9N	2.8W	19:11:53	252	11.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	
Profile 6.1	19:11:53	252	11.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	19:13:55	247	9.1kft	51.1N	1.7W	
Profile 6.2	19:13:56	247	9.1kft	51.1N	1.7W	19:18:11	247	13.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	
Profile 6.3	19:18:11	247	13.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	19:22:41	247	9.1kft	51.0N	2.4W	
Profile 6.4	19:22:41	247	9.1kft	51.0N	2.4W	19:27:04	260	13.2kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 7	19:27:04	260	13.2kft	50.9N	2.8W	19:33:43	079	20.0kft	51.0N	2.1W	
Profile 8	19:33:43	079	20.0kft	51.0N	2.1W	19:35:48	079	18.1kft	51.1N	1.8W	
Run 6	19:35:48	079	18.1kft	51.1N	1.8W	19:43:42	245	18.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	
Profile 9	19:43:43	245	18.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	19:59:09	102	30.1kft	51.0N	2.7W	
Run 7	19:59:09	102	30.1kft	51.0N	2.7W	20:02:02	096	30.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	Waters zeroed at 19:58
Run 8	20:04:19	077	25.1kft	51.1N	1.9W	20:13:20	246	25.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	
note	20:07:27	081	25.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chulbolton
Profile 10.1	20:15:00	252	20.1kft	51.1N	1.7W	20:18:46	246	16.1kft	51.0N	2.0W	
Profile 10.2	20:18:46	246	16.1kft	51.0N	2.0W	20:22:44	245	19.9kft	51.0N	2.4W	
Profile 10.3	20:22:44	245	19.9kft	51.0N	2.4W	20:26:44	313	15.9kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 11	20:26:44	313	15.9kft	50.9N	2.8W	20:33:07	079	9.1kft	51.0N	2.1W	
Run 9	20:33:07	079	9.1kft	51.0N	2.1W	20:44:20	251	9.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	
note	20:39:02	079	9.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chulb
Profile 12.1	20:44:20	251	9.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	20:50:01	253	4.1kft	51.0N	2.0W	P12.1 actually started 20:44:44
Profile 12.2	20:50:01	253	4.1kft	51.0N	2.0W	20:54:07	252	7.9kft	51.0N	2.4W	P12.1 actually started 20:44:44
Profile 12.3	20:54:08	252	7.9kft	51.0N	2.4W	20:56:19	253	6.1kft	50.9N	2.6W	